

“Undergraduates' Perception of the Challenges of E-learning in Universities in Kwara State, Nigeria

Abstract

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into higher education has created new opportunities for teaching and learning, yet its adoption in Nigeria is still hindered by significant barriers. This study explored undergraduates' perceptions of the challenges associated with e-learning in universities across Kwara State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was employed, and a sample of 396 undergraduates was drawn from selected universities. Data were collected using a researcher-developed instrument, the Students' Challenges Towards E-learning Questionnaire (SCTEQ), which demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.73. Findings revealed that students encountered difficulties such as limited face-to-face interaction, high internet subscription costs, inadequate access to learning devices, eye strain from prolonged screen use, and challenges with online participation. Results further indicated significant differences in the challenges experienced based on gender, place of residence, age, and academic level. The study recommends that university administrators provide affordable internet access, enhance digital infrastructure, and organize digital literacy workshops to support students in effectively engaging with online learning platforms.

Keywords: E-learning, ICT, challenges, Undergraduates, Kwara State

Introduction

In recent years, higher education institutions worldwide have increasingly adopted e-learning as a means of expanding access to education and enhancing flexibility in teaching and learning. Research suggests that digital platforms enable institutions to reach wider populations, including individuals in remote areas who may otherwise lack access to conventional universities (Liu & Yu, 2023). Furthermore, online learning allows universities to scale educational delivery without excessive investment in physical infrastructure, while providing students with the flexibility to learn at their own pace and location (Alam, 2021).

The application of ICT in education has also been shown to improve teaching, learning, and research by enriching students' experiences and aligning school practices with workplace realities (Yusuf, 2015). However, despite these benefits, the adoption of ICT and e-learning in many developing nations, particularly in Africa, remains limited due to infrastructural, economic, and human capacity challenges (Nannim, Yushau, & Gital, 2018).

In Nigeria, efforts to mainstream e-learning have been met with mixed outcomes. While some institutions have recorded progress, others face persistent barriers such as poor internet infrastructure, inadequate training, and limited institutional support. These challenges have raised concerns regarding the readiness of both students and lecturers to effectively use digital platforms for teaching and learning. Consequently, understanding students' perceptions of these challenges is essential in order to design practical solutions that can improve the quality of e-learning.

Statement of problem

The integration of e-learning into higher education has been hampered by persistent infrastructural and attitudinal challenges. In Nigeria, unreliable electricity supply, poor internet connectivity, high subscription costs, and limited access to digital devices remain key barriers that hinder effective participation in online learning (Ikediugwu, 2023). These challenges often discourage students and widen inequalities in access to education.

Underfunding of the education sector further compounds the problem. Federal allocations to education have remained below UNESCO's 15–20% benchmark, limiting investments in ICT infrastructure, lecturer training, and the development of sustainable e-learning initiatives (Nwokolo et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2024). Consequently, the necessary support systems for effective online learning are inadequate.

Empirical evidence reinforces these concerns. Studies in Nigeria have shown that while some students view e-learning positively, many remain indifferent or resistant due to connectivity issues, erratic electricity, and lack of face-to-face interaction (Olajide, Anyakora, & Ojo, 2023). Similar challenges have been reported internationally, with students in Malaysia, for example, expressing preference for traditional classrooms because of technical difficulties in online platforms (Karismajeet et al., 2022).

These unresolved challenges highlight the need to investigate undergraduates' perceptions of e-learning in Nigerian universities. Without addressing these barriers, e-learning may fall short of its potential to enhance equitable access and improve academic outcomes.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the challenges and attitude of undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study:

1. What are the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on gender and place of residence
2. There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on age.
3. There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on academic level.

Literature Review

E-learning is a broad concept that encompasses different modes of delivering instruction through digital technologies Patel (2016) categorized e-learning into four main types: individualized self-paced learning online, individualized self-paced learning offline, group-based synchronous learning, and group-based asynchronous learning. The first category allows learners to access resources through the internet at their own pace, while the offline version involves learning from stored resources such as CDs or hard drives without internet connectivity. Group-based synchronous learning occurs in real time, using tools such as video conferencing or live chats, whereas asynchronous learning allows participants to engage in discussions or access content at different times, often through online forums or learning management systems. Recent studies have emphasized that the rise of digital learning platforms and mobile technologies has expanded these forms, making hybrid and blended models increasingly popular in higher education (Samuratova, 2023).

Adoption and Challenges of E-learning

Despite the benefits, the adoption of e-learning in higher education remains uneven, particularly between developed and developing countries. In contexts with strong digital infrastructure, students generally embrace e-learning due to its flexibility and accessibility (Eltahir, 2019). However, in developing regions, persistent challenges continue to hinder effective implementation.

Scholars have categorized these challenges into technological, individual, cultural, and institutional dimensions (Kanwal & Rehman, 2017; Tarus, Gichoya, & Muumbo, 2015). Technological barriers include poor network infrastructure, unreliable electricity supply, and

limited access to digital devices. On an individual level, issues such as lack of ICT competence, low digital literacy, and limited internet experience often reduce students' readiness to adopt online platforms (Chen & Tseng, 2022). Cultural and contextual differences also shape the perception of online learning, while institutional challenges such as inadequate technical support and weak policy frameworks further exacerbate the situation (Mulhanga & Lima, 2017).

In sub-Saharan Africa, studies have shown that e-learning adoption is constrained by financial limitations, lack of training, and poor digital resources (Aung & Khaing, 2015; Adnan & Anwar, 2020). For example, Olukayode (2015) observed that Nigerian students face difficulties such as insufficient computer facilities, high cost of data, and frequent power outages. Similarly, more recent evidence indicates that students struggle with the affordability of internet subscriptions, lack of institutional support, and limited lecturer preparedness to handle online teaching (Coman et al., 2020; Smith & Johnson, 2022).

Global and Local Perspectives

Globally, platforms such as Coursera, Khan Academy, and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have transformed access to education by making quality learning content available to diverse populations (Aliakbari & Hassen, 2022). However, despite this global expansion, scholars argue that adoption in many Nigerian universities remains slow. Factors such as the high economic costs of implementing e-learning, weak ICT infrastructure in rural areas, and insufficient technical expertise among faculty members continue to limit progress (Nannim, Yushau, & Gital, 2018; Mashinini, 2020). Recent Nigerian studies (Abugu, Chidi, Eze, & Ufodiama, 2025; Joseph, Ayoola, & Salihu, 2025)

reveal that while students are aware of the potential of online learning, practical usage is hindered by affordability, unstable internet connectivity, and limited institutional support. These findings align with international evidence that effective adoption depends not only on technology but also on the preparedness of both students and instructors to engage meaningfully with digital platforms (Baran & Correia, 2019).

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study:

2. What are the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study:

4. There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on gender and place of residence
5. There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on age.
6. There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on academic level.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design, which is appropriate for exploring the perceptions of a large population on specific issues. The design was chosen because it allows for

the collection of quantitative data from undergraduates to determine the challenges they face when engaging in e-learning in Kwara State universities.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised all undergraduate students enrolled in universities across Kwara State. According to the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (2023), the total undergraduate population in the state is approximately 107,632. Using Research Advisor (2006) guidelines for sample size determination at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, a minimum of 383 respondents was required. To account for possible attrition, the sample was increased to 396 undergraduates. Respondents were drawn from both a public and a private university to ensure wider representation.

Instrumentation

Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Students' Challenges Towards E-learning Questionnaire (SCTEQ). The instrument was designed to capture students' experiences, perceptions, and challenges regarding e-learning. Items in the questionnaire were structured on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a test-retest procedure was conducted, and the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) produced a coefficient of 0.73, indicating acceptable reliability.

Validity

The face and content validity of the instrument were established by three experts in Educational Technology and Guidance and Counselling. Their input ensured that the items accurately reflected the constructs under study.

Data Collection Procedure

Questionnaires were administered physically and electronically to sampled students with the assistance of research assistants. Ethical considerations such as informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation were strictly observed throughout the data collection process.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean and standard deviation were applied to answer the research questions, while independent sample t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State?

The responses of students regarding the challenges they encountered while using e-learning are summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and Rank Order of Challenges Faced by Undergraduates

Item No	Challenge Encountered:	Mean	S.D.	Rank
7	Lack of face-to-face interaction with my colleagues	3.29	.89	1 st
6	High expenditure on internet subscriptions	3.27	.79	2 nd
14	high cost of personal e-learning devices (e.g., laptops, smart phones)	3.17	.98	3 rd
12	Eye strain due to prolonged screen use	3.12	1.02	4 th
8	inability to fully participate in online classes	3.11	.91	5 th
15	Higher cost of practical e-learning compared to traditional methods	3.11	.924	5 th
11	Limited training on how to use e-learning tools	3.06	1.01	7 th
4	Lecturers' limited technical competence	2.95	.95	8 th

2	lack of supporting devices (e.g., laptop, smart boards)	2.92	.81	9 th
1	no proper orientation on e-learning usage	2.88	.88	10 th
13	lack of timely feedback from lecturers	2.88	1.03	10 th
5	Difficulty in practicing what was taught	2.82	1.08	12 th
10	Overload of digital texts (e.g., PDFs)	2.80	1.02	13 th
3	poor internet connectivity	2.77	1.00	14 th
9	Inadequate institutional support for e-learning	2.56	1.03	15 th

Interpretation:

Table 1 shows that the most prominent challenges were the lack of social interaction with colleagues (Mean = 3.29), high internet subscription costs (Mean = 3.27), and the cost of purchasing e-learning devices (Mean =3.17). on the other hand, challenges such as poor internet connection (Mean = 2.77) and weak institutional support (Mean =2.56) were ranked lower, though still above the cut-off mean of 2.50. This indicates that all the listed items were recognized as challenges by the respondents.

Hypothesis One: *There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on gender and place of residence.*

Table 2: T.test Analysis of Challenges Based on Gender and Residence

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	Cal.	t-	Crit.	t-	p-value
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					value	value	
Male	138	46.65	7.989	394	3.84*	1.96	.000*
Female	258	43.74	6.701				
Off campus	312	46.05	5.933	394	7.26*	1.96	.000*
On campus	84	39.93	9.58				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Interpretation:

Table 2 reveals that male students reported significantly higher levels of challenges compared to their female counterparts ($t = 3.84, p < .05$). Likewise, off campus students experienced more difficulties with e-learning compared to those living on campus ($t = 7.26, p < .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: *There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on age*

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Based on Age

Source	Sum of Squares	df	MS	Cal. F	Crit. F	P-value
Between Groups	1000.25	2	500.125	9.80*	3.00	0.00
Within Groups	20194.99	393	51.01			
Total	21045.24	395				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Interpretation:

The ANOVA result indicates that significant differences exist across age groups ($F = 9.80$, $p < .05$). Post-hoc analysis (Scheffe test) showed that students aged **31 years and above** reported more severe challenges compared to younger age groups.

Table 4: Scheffe post-hoc where the significant difference lies based on Age

Years	N	Sub set for Alpha = 0.05		
		1	2	3
16-25 years	180	43.3		
26-30 years	186		45.61	
31 years and above	30			48.60
Sig.		.152	.053	

Table 4 reveals that respondents who were between 16-25 years and those between 26-30

years of age had the mean scores of 43.23 and 45.61 (in subset 1 and 2), while those who 31 years of age and above had the highest mean scores of 48.60 (in subset 3) and thus, contributed to the significant difference.

Hypothesis Three: *There is no significant difference in the challenges faced by undergraduates towards e-learning in Kwara State based on academic level*

Table 5: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Challenges Based on Academic Level

Source	Sum of Squares	df	MS	Cal. F	Crit. F	P-value
Between Groups	1872.85	4	468.21	9.54*	2.37	.000
Within Groups	19172.40	391	49.03			
Total	21045.24	395				

*Significant, $p < 0.05$

Interpretation:

The analysis indicates significant differences across academic levels ($F = 9.54$, $p < .05$). Further post-hoc testing revealed that **500-level students** reported the highest levels of challenges compared to lower-level students.

Table 6: Scheffe post-hoc where the significant difference lies based on Academic Level

Level	N	Sub set for Alpha = 0.05				
		1	2	3	4	5
200	84	41.4				
100	30		42.0			

400	48	45.38	
300	20	45.65	
500	36		48.83
Sig.	1.00	.071	.189

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight several persistent challenges that undergraduates encounter while engaging in e-learning in Kwara State. The most pressing issues identified were lack of face-to-face interaction with peers, high costs of internet subscriptions and digital devices, and health-related concerns such as eye strain. These findings align with previous studies across Africa, which have consistently pointed to poor ICT infrastructure, high data costs, and inadequate digital literacy as barriers to online learning (Eze et al., 2018; Adnan & Anwar, 2020).

The results further revealed significant gender-based differences in the challenges faced. Male students reported experiencing more difficulties compared to females, a finding consistent with Smith and Johnson (2022), who noted that female students often adapt better to the social aspects of online learning, though they may report higher anxiety during online assessments. Residence was also a critical factor, with students living off campus encountering more difficulties than their on-campus peers due to weaker internet connectivity and unstable power supply. Similar observations have been made in other Nigerian studies where off-campus students struggled with poor network access and limited access to university-provided ICT facilities (Joseph, Ayoola, &

Salihu,

2025).

Age was another differentiating factor, with older students (31 years and above) reporting greater challenges than younger cohorts. This supports findings by Chen, Hsu, and Kao (2019), who suggested that older students are less digitally inclined due to limited prior exposure to emerging technologies. Likewise, the significant differences observed across academic levels—with final-year (500-level) students facing more challenges—may be attributed to the higher academic demands placed on them. This aligns with Baran and Correia (2019), who argued that advanced students often encounter greater pressure in meeting academic requirements, which is compounded by technological disruptions.

Overall, these findings reinforce the notion that while e-learning has potential to improve educational access and flexibility, its success in Nigeria is highly dependent on context-specific challenges such as affordability, infrastructural readiness, and user competence.

Conclusion

This study examined the challenges of e-learning among undergraduates in Kwara State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that despite the growing importance of digital learning platforms, undergraduates continue to face significant obstacles including high internet costs, inadequate access to devices, poor digital skills, and limited interaction with peers and lecturers. These challenges varied significantly by gender, residence, age, and academic level, underscoring the need for context-sensitive interventions.

The study concludes that unless infrastructural and human-capacity barriers are addressed, the potential of e-learning to enhance access to quality higher education in Nigeria will remain underutilized.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Improved Infrastructure:** University management, in collaboration with government and private stakeholders, should provide affordable and reliable internet services within campuses to reduce the burden of data costs.
2. **Device Accessibility Programs:** Institutions should initiate subsidy schemes, instalment plans, or partnerships with technology companies to make laptops, tablets, and smartphones more affordable for students.
3. **Capacity Building:** Workshops and digital literacy training should be organized for both students and lecturers to improve competence in using e-learning platforms.
4. **Support Systems:** Academic counsellors should establish peer-support groups and mentoring programs to address the issue of social isolation associated with online learning.

5. Policy Development: Universities and regulatory bodies should formulate clear e-learning policies that address equity, accessibility, and inclusion, particularly for disadvantaged groups such as rural-based students and those with disabilities.

6. Further Research: Future studies should explore the long-term psychological and academic impacts of e-learning challenges on undergraduates in Nigeria, with particular attention to mental health and academic performance.

REFERENCES

Adnan, M., & Anwar, K. (2020). Online learning amid the COVID-19 pandemic: Students' perspectives. *Journal of Pedagogical Sociology and Psychology*, 2 (1), 45-51.

<https://doi.org/10.33902/JPSP.2020261309>

Alam, A. (2021, December). Cloud-based e-learning: development of conceptual model for adaptive e-learning ecosystem based on cloud computing infrastructure. In *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Data Science* (pp. 377-391). Springer.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90615-3_30

Aliakbari, M., & Hassen, Q. K. (2022). The Expectations and Reality of E-Learning. *Mediterranean Journal of Social & Behavioral Research*, 6(2), 61-66.

<https://doi.org/10.30935/mjosbr/11926>

Aung, T. N. & Khaing, S. S. (2015). *Challenges of implementing e-learning in developing countries: A review. In International Conference on Genetic and Evolutionary Computing* (pp. 405-411). Springer, Cham.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-23207-2_41

Baran, E., & Correia, A. P. (2019). Student-led approaches in online learning: Implications for online instructional design practice. *Online Learning*, 23(4), 34-54.

<https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v23i4.2077>

Casement, W. (2018). Will online learning lower the price for college? *Journal of college admission*, 15-18.

Chen, H. R., & Tseng, H. F. (2022). Factors that influence acceptance of web-based e-learning systems for the in-service education of junior high school teachers in Taiwan. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 35(3), 398–406.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2011.11.007>

Chen, K., Hsu, Y., & Kao, C. (2019). Examining older adults' intention to use e-learning services: Applying the technology acceptance model. *Educational Gerontology*, 45(11), 657–670.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/03601277.2019.1689305>

Coman, C., Tiru, L. G., Schmitz, L. M., Stanciu, C., & Bularca, M. C. (2020).

Online teaching and learning in higher education during the coronavirus pandemic: Students' perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10367 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410367>

Crossley, S. A., & McNamara, D. S. (2017). Adaptive educational technologies for literacy instruction. *Routledge*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315647500>

Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crisis.

Journal of Educational Technology Systems, 49(1), 5–22.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>

Eltahir, M. E. (2019). E-learning in developing countries: Is it a panacea?

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2928019>

Eze, S. C., Chinedu-Eze, V. C., & Bello, A. O. (2018). The utilization of e-learning facilities in the educational delivery system of Nigeria: A study of M-University. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-018-0116-z>

Gillett-Swan, J. (2017). The challenges of online learning: Supporting and engaging the isolated learner. *Journal of Learning Design*, 10(1), 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.5204/jld.v9i3.293>

Gilbert, B. (2015). Online learning revealing the benefits and challenges. 303, 2056. https://fisherpub.sjfc.edu/education_ETD_masters/303

Gokah, T. K., Gupta, N., & Ndiweni, E. (2015). E-learning in higher education. Opportunities and challenges for Dubai. *International Journal on E-learning*, 14(4), [443–470](#).

Joseph, O. J., Ayoola, T. J., & Salihu, I. (2025). Digital learning and student engagement in Nigerian universities: Challenges and prospects. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research*, 19(2), 55–68.

Kanwal, F., & Rehman, M. (2017). Factors affecting e-learning adoption in developing countries: Empirical evidence from Pakistan's higher education sector. *IEEE Access*, 5, [1096810978](#). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2714379>

Liu, M., & Yu, D. (2023). Towards intelligent e-learning systems. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(7), 78457876. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11852->

Mashinini, V. (2020). COVID-19 and the National University of Lesotho:

- Experiences and challenges. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 8(9), 157–180.
- Mulhanga, M. M., & Lima, S. R. (2017). Podcast as e-learning enabler for developing countries: Current initiatives, challenges and trends. In *Proceedings of the 2017. 9th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers* (pp. 126–130). ACM. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3175536.3175549>
- Musingafi, M., Mapuranga, B., Chiwanza, K., & Zebron, S. (2015). Challenges for open and distance learning (ODL) students: Experiences from Zimbabwe Open University. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(18), 60–65.
- Nannim, F. A., Yushau, B., & Gital, A. Y. (2018). Lecturers' awareness and use of ICT facilities for teaching in Nigerian universities. *African Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education*, 4(1), 16–24.
- Olukayode, S. A. (2015). Challenges and prospects of e-learning at the National Open University of Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 9(3), [207–216](https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v9i3.1724). <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v9i3.1724>
- Palvia, S., Aeron, P., Gupta, P., Mahapatra, D., Parida, R., & Rosner, R. (2018). Online education worldwide: Status, challenges, trends, and implications. *Journal of Global Information Technology Management*, 21(4), [233–241](https://doi.org/10.1080/1097198X.2018.1542262). <https://doi.org/10.1080/1097198X.2018.1542262>
- Samuratova, T. K. (2023). Modern methods of teaching computer programs in the education system. *Journal of Educational Technology and Innovation*, 3(2), 45–57.
- Sarvestani, M. S., Mohammadi, M., Afshin, J., & Raeisy, L. (2019). Students' experiences of e-learning challenges: A phenomenological study. *Interdisciplinary Journal*

of Virtual Learning in Medical Sciences, 10(3), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.30476/IJVLMS.2019.82318>.

Smith, L., & Johnson, R. (2022). Gendered experiences of online learning during COVID-19 in Africa. *African Journal of Education and Development*, 8(1), 101–116.

Tarus, J. K., Gichoya, D., & Muumbo, A. (2015). Challenges of implementing e-learning in Kenya: A case of public universities. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 16(1), 120–

Yusuf, M. O. (2015). Information and communication technologies in education: Analyzing the Nigerian national policy. *International Education Journal*, 6(3), 316–321.